

Mitigation of biochemical and histological effects of bromobenzene on the hepatic system in rats by the Indian herbal drug formulation Triphala

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Abstract : The present study is an attempt to evaluate the hepatoprotective and anti-oxidant properties of Triphala against bromobenzene (BB) induced hepatotoxicity in rats. Hepatotoxicity was induced in rats by a single oral dose of BB (10 mmol/kg b.w) on first day of the study. Two different doses (250 mg/kg b.w and 500 mg/kg b.w) of Triphala were administered to the bromobenzene intoxicated rats for 8 days. The standard hepatoprotective drug silymarin was used as reference drug for comparison. Bromobenzene treatment resulted in a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the activities of anti-oxidant enzymes; catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione-S-transferase (GST), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and total reduced glutathione (Reduced GSH) levels. There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, serum bilirubin, and liver functional markers; alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate transaminase (AST) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP). The administration of two different doses (250 mg/kg b.w and 500 mg/kg b.w) of Triphala in BB-treated rats normalized the tested parameters in a dose dependent manner indicating its hepatoprotective activity. The histopathological examinations of liver sections of the rats support the biochemical observation.

Keywords : Bromobenzene, hepatotoxicity, Triphala, antioxidant.

Introduction

Bromobenzene (BB) is a xenobiotic compound and an industrial solvent which induces hepatic necrosis in living beings¹. BB is converted to its reactive metabolites in liver which conjugate with glutathione (GSH), thus reducing the hepatic GSH and also impairing the protection against reactive oxygen species (ROS)^{2,3}. There is a strong correlation between GSH depletion, lipid peroxidation and the development of liver necrosis⁴.

Triphala is one of the most common herbal formulations used in Indian ayurvedic medicine and comprises of the three fruits, *Terminalia bellerica*, *Terminalia chebula* and *Embllica officinalis*. It has diverse medicinal properties and possesses anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, anti-malarial, anti-viral, anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, hepatoprotective, gastroprotective and anti-ageing activity⁵⁻¹¹. The present study was undertaken to establish the hepatoprotective effect of Triphala in BB-induced hepatotoxicity in rats.

Experimental

Animals and drug treatment :

Female albino-Wistar rats weighing about 153 ± 13 g were obtained from the animal house, VIT University, Vellore, India. The rats were allocated in 5 groups of six animals as follows : Group I (control group) : rats received 1.5 ml of coconut oil on day 1 and normal food and water after that until the end of the experiment. Group II (BB group) : toxicity was induced by a single oral dose of 10 mmol/kg body weight BB dissolved in coconut oil, after which normal food and water was given till day 8. Group III : rats received a single oral dose of BB (10 mmol/kg body weight) and treated with Triphala (250 mg/kg body weight) one hour after BB administration and also for the following 7 days. Group IV : rats received a single oral dose of BB (10 mmol/kg body weight) and treated with Triphala (500 mg/kg body weight) one hour after BB administration and also for the following 7 days. Group V : rats received a single oral dose of BB (10 mmol/kg body weight) and treated with the standard

drug silymarin (100 mg/kg body weight) one hour after BB administration and also for the following 7 days. After 18 h the animals were sacrificed and blood and liver was collected.

Serum parameters :

The levels of AST, ALT and ALP, total cholesterol, triglycerides, total and direct bilirubin were determined in the serum of the animals using commercial diagnostic kits (Span Diagnostics, India) according to the manufacturer's protocol.

Antioxidant status :

Assays of antioxidant enzymes like the catalase (CAT)¹⁴, superoxide dismutase (SOD)¹⁵, glutathione-S-transferase (G-S-T)¹⁶, glutathione peroxidase (GPx)¹⁷ and total reduced glutathione (Reduced GSH)¹⁸ and the lipid peroxidation (LPO) levels¹⁹ were determined in plasma.

Histopathological examination :

A portion of the liver of all experimental animals was fixed in 10% formalin immediately after sacrifice. The tissue was washed and then dehydrated in descending grades of isopropanol and finally with xylene. The tissues were then embedded in paraffin wax and sections of 5 μ m thickness were cut. The sections were stained with haematoxylin and eosin and observed microscopically for histopathological changes.

Results and discussion

Serum parameters :

The increased levels of liver functional markers observed in BB intoxicated rats has been due to the damaged structural integrity of the liver as they are released into circulation after cellular damage¹². The rats treated with bromobenzene alone (Group II) developed severe hepatocellular injuries which is indicated by significant ($p < 0.05$) elevation in serum AST, ALT and ALP activities when compared to the normal control group (see Table 1). However, treatment with Triphala (250 mg/kg b.w and 500 mg/kg b.w) normalized these alterations to levels similar to that of the normal control rats. The membrane stabilizing effect of Triphala might prevent the leakage of these intracellular enzymes into circulation. Elevated levels of serum bilirubin indicate hepatobiliary disease and severely disturbed hepatocellular function¹³. Liver injury induced by BB was evident from the signifi-

cant ($p < 0.05$) elevated levels of serum total and direct bilirubin in the bromobenzene treated group. By contrast, the bilirubin levels are reduced in the Triphala treated groups (Group III and IV) significantly ($p < 0.05$) which is near to that of the control group (see Table 1). Significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the levels of serum total cholesterol and triglycerides were seen in the BB-intoxicated rats. Triphala treatment normalized the elevated serum total cholesterol and triglycerides levels.

Anti-oxidant activity :

The formation of reactive metabolites and oxidative stress result in the damage of liver in BB-treated rats, which can be observed by the significant reduction in the anti-oxidant status of BB-treated rats. The rats treated with bromobenzene (Group II) showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the anti-oxidant enzymes (catalase, SOD, GST and GPx) and total reduced glutathione (see Table 2). However, treatment with Triphala (Group III and IV) significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased the anti-oxidant status as compared to that of the control group (Group I). Increased lipid peroxidation was observed in the bromobenzene treated group which was significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the control group. On the other hand, Triphala significantly ($p < 0.05$) reversed the lipid peroxidation to normal as that of the control rats (see Table 2). Silymarin also showed increased activities of anti-oxidant enzymes and total reduced glutathione levels.

Liver histopathology :

The hepatoprotective effect of Triphala against bromobenzene induced toxicity was confirmed by histopathological examination of the liver tissue of control and treated animals (see Fig. 1). The histological architecture of control rats (Group I) was found to be normal with a central vein surrounded by distinct hepatic cells with clear granular cytoplasm. The liver sections of bromobenzene treated rats (Group II) showed enlarged hepatocytes, vacuolated cytoplasm and large nuclei with condensed chromatin. However, Triphala treated rats (Group III and IV) appear to prevent the bromobenzene induced hepatotoxicity showing the central vein and hepatocytes with clear ballooning cytoplasm. Silymarin treated rats (Group V) also exhibited protection against bromobenzene toxicity less disarrangement, normal degenerative hepatocytes and reactive hepatocytes.

Table 1. Effect of Triphala on AST, ALT ALP, bilirubin, total cholesterol and triglyceride levels in serum of BB intoxicated rats

Parameters	Group I (Control)	Group II (BB 10 mmol/kg)	Group III (BB + Triphala 250 mg/kg b.w)	Group IV (BB + Triphala 500 mg/kg b.w)	Group V (BB + Silymarin 100 mg/kg b.w)
AST (IU/L)	71.15 ± 2.01	142.43 ± 2.05 ^{a*}	76.85 ± 1.55 ^{a*b*}	77.28 ± 2.43 ^{a*b*}	76.68 ± 1.55 ^{a*b*}
ALT (IU/L)	88.95 ± 2.26	168.04 ± 3.69 ^{a*}	94.31 ± 2.06 ^{a*b*}	97.43 ± 3.08 ^{a*b*}	89.54 ± 3.81 ^{b*d*}
ALP (K.A. units/L)	126.97 ± 2.70	327.87 ± 4.56 ^{a*}	139.96 ± 2.58 ^{a*b*}	133.58 ± 2.72 ^{a*b*c*}	135.66 ± 1.99 ^{a*b*}
Total bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.77 ± 0.06	6.30 ± 0.29 ^{a*}	0.92 ± 0.07 ^{b*}	1.03 ± 0.12 ^{a*b*}	0.92 ± 0.06 ^{b*}
Direct bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.58 ± 0.08	4.03 ± 0.65 ^{a*}	0.58 ± 0.09 ^{b*}	0.65 ± 0.13 ^{b*}	0.60 ± 0.11 ^{b*}
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	74.39 ± 1.77	126.85 ± 2.44 ^{a*}	81.53 ± 1.74 ^{a*b*}	79.29 ± 1.41 ^{a*b*}	78.88 ± 1.68 ^{a*b*}
Triglycerides (mg/dl)	88.60 ± 1.08	197.90 ± 1.95 ^{a*}	105.60 ± 1.14 ^{a*b*}	108.25 ± 1.14 ^{a*b*c*}	107.21 ± 1.13 ^{a*b*}

N=6 animals in each group. The values are expressed as mean ± S.D. Comparisons indicated by lower case letters were made as follows : a – group I vs group II, III, IV and V; b – group II vs group III, IV and V; c – group III vs group IV and V; d – group IV vs group V. Statistical analysis was carried out by one way ANOVA followed by Student's Newman-Kuel's test. The symbols represent statistical significance at : **p* < 0.05.

Table 2. Effect of Triphala on the activities of anti-oxidant enzymes and lipid peroxidation levels in the plasma of BB intoxicated rats

Parameters	Group I (Control)	Group II (BB 10 mmol/kg)	Group III (BB + Triphala 250 mg/kg b.w)	Group IV (BB + Triphala 500 mg/kg b.w)	Group V (BB + Silymarin 100 mg/kg b.w)
CAT	11.98 ± 0.83	7.03 ± 0.67 ^{a*}	11.78 ± 0.44 ^{b*}	11.05 ± 0.59 ^{b*}	11.98 ± 0.48 ^{b*}
GPx	68.26 ± 1.95	37.06 ± 1.11 ^{a*}	66.03 ± 1.08 ^{b*}	64.90 ± 1.28 ^{a*b*}	67.11 ± 1.04 ^{b*}
SOD	225.71 ± 1.71	116.23 ± 1.99 ^{a*}	227.19 ± 1.56 ^{b*}	231.27 ± 1.87 ^{a*b*c*}	229.90 ± 1.49 ^{a*b*}
G-S-T	87.08 ± 1.54	62.61 ± 2.02 ^{a*}	83.60 ± 1.30 ^{a*b*}	84.38 ± 1.85 ^{b*}	89.49 ± 1.22 ^{b*c*d*}
Reduced GSH	48.70 ± 1.26	24.09 ± 1.52 ^{a*}	48.57 ± 0.52 ^{b*}	46.85 ± 1.31 ^{b*}	46.10 ± 0.50 ^{a*b*c*}
LPO	1.29 ± 0.08	2.51 ± 0.15 ^{a*}	1.50 ± 0.17 ^{b*}	1.40 ± 0.11 ^{b*}	1.26 ± 0.10 ^{b*c*}

N=6 animals in each group. The values are expressed as mean ± S.D. Comparisons indicated by lower case letters were made as follows : a – group I vs group II, III, IV and V; b – group II vs group III, IV and V; c – group III vs group IV and V; d – group IV vs group V. Statistical analysis was carried out by one way ANOVA followed by Student's Newman-Kuel's test. The symbols represent statistical significance at : **p* < 0.05. Units : CAT - micromoles of H₂O₂ consumed/min/mg protein; GPx - µg of GSH utilized/min/mg protein; SOD - units/mg protein (1 U = amount of enzyme that inhibit the autoxidation of pyrogallol by 50%); GST - nmol of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene - GSH conjugate formed/min/mg protein; Reduced glutathione - nmol/mg protein; LPO - nmol of MDA formed/mg protein.

Fig. 1. Histopathological analysis of the hepatoprotective effect of Triphala against bromobenzene-induced toxicity in rats (H&E 20X). (a) Group 1 (control rats) shows normal morphology and hepatocytes arranged around the central vein. (b) Group 2 (bromobenzene 10 mmol/kg b.w-induced rats) shows enlarged and oedematous hepatocytes. (c, d) Group 3 (bromobenzene 10 mmol/kg b.w + Triphala 250 mg/kg b.w) and Group 4 (bromobenzene 10 mmol/kg b.w + Triphala 500 mg/kg b.w) shows normal architecture of liver with feathery changes and mild degeneration respectively. (e) Group 5 (bromobenzene 10 mmol/kg b.w + silymarin 100 mg/kg b.w) shows improvement over bromobenzene-induced group with mild oedema.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the present study demonstrates that the Indian ayurvedic formulation Triphala exerts significant protective effects against BB-induced hepatotoxicity by augmenting host antioxidant defense mechanisms. However, further pharmacological evidence is required to establish the mechanism of action of this potential herbal drug. Studies at molecular level would reveal the pathways through which Triphala acts to restore the hepatic GSH pool and levels of antioxidant enzymes and prevents lipid peroxidation and necrosis.

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